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SMARTNESS promotes Immersive Reality workshop for public school students as part of the “Olhos no Futuro” project

SMARTNESS took part in the 7th edition of the “Olhos no Futuro” project, promoted by UNICAMP in partnership with CPTEn. We welcomed 28 students from the “Dr. Telêmaco Paioli Melges” School (Sumaré-SP) for the “Immersive Reality” workshop, featuring lab visits and hands-on experiences with virtual reality technologies. The initiative is part of our ongoing efforts to connect youth with science and education.

[Read more](#)

SMARTNESS Researchers Stand Out at NetSoft 2025 in Budapest

SMARTNESS researchers took part in IEEE NetSoft 2025 in Budapest, presenting six works across the PhD Symposium and Demo Sessions, covering topics such as programmable networks and edge-delivered streaming. In addition, Prof. Christian Rothenberg delivered a keynote at ENS 2025. The participation was highlighted by the Best Demo Paper Award for a work on holographic streaming with programmable testbeds.

[Read more](#)

SMARTNESS Researchers Visit Ericsson in Budapest to Strengthen Academic-Industry Collaboration

On June 20, 2025, SMARTNESS researchers visited Ericsson House in Budapest ahead of their participation in NetSoft 2025. The visit strengthened ties between SMARTNESS and Ericsson through technical exchanges on topics like TSN, neuromorphic computing, and DESIRE6G. Students and researchers shared their ongoing work and received valuable feedback, reinforcing collaboration and contributing to their professional development.

[Read more](#)

SMARTNESS welcomes Siemens delegation to explore technological collaboration

On June 24, 2025, SMARTNESS received a visit from Siemens Energy executives from Brazil and the USA. The delegation met with Dr. Eduardo Sartori and learned about the center's research and lab facilities. Researchers presented technologies aligned with Siemens' areas of interest, such as resilient grids and decarbonized processes, opening space for potential collaboration.

[Read more](#)

SMARTNESS showcases immersive communication experiment at the “FT de Portas Abertas” event

SMARTNESS took part in the FT de Portas Abertas event at Unicamp Limeira with an immersive communication experiment. The activity was coordinated by Prof. Vanessa Testoni and carried out by students Alan Teixeira da Silva (PhD) and Rafael Pedrosa Silva Clerici (Master’s). It attracted over 400 visitors, with more than 50 actively engaging in the demo.

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SMARTNESS Researchers Participate in SBRC 2025

SMARTNESS researchers joined NOMS 2025 in Honolulu, sharing advances in edge computing, XR offloading, and 5G video streaming. Highlights included a full paper on decomposing monolithic applications for distributed execution, a demo on XR offloading via WebAssembly, and a study on 5G channel metrics and video QoE. The event showcased key contributions from the DisCoNet and C3LA research strands.

[Read more](#)

Smartness Researchers Highlight Advances in Application Decomposition and 5G Video Streaming Experience at NOMS 2025

SMARTNESS researchers joined NOMS 2025 in Honolulu, sharing advances in edge computing, XR offloading, and 5G video streaming. Highlights included a full paper on decomposing monolithic applications for distributed execution, a demo on XR offloading via WebAssembly, and a study on 5G channel metrics and video QoE. The event showcased key contributions from the DisCoNet and C3LA research strands.

[Read more](#)

SMARTNESS Hosts ANATEL-CEADI for Technical Visit and Institutional Exchange

On May 15, SMARTNESS hosted a technical and institutional visit from ANATEL-CEADI. Led by Eng. João Marcelo Mello da Silva and welcomed by Dr. Eduardo Sartori, the visit included a presentation of SMARTNESS activities, a tour of the laboratories, and a productive exchange on potential synergies in research and development in the field of telecommunications.

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FEEC Students Visit SMARTNESS Lab and Explore Future Technologies

Undergraduate students from FEEC/UNICAMP visited the SMARTNESS lab on May 9 for a guided tour of research activities. The visit included a robotics presentation by PhD student Felipe Mota and demonstrations of drone systems and immersive media by PhD students Mauricio Rodriguez and Alan Teixeira da Silva. The activity sparked great interest and strengthened the connection between education and innovation.

[Read more](#)

Prof. Christian Rothenberg Presents SMARTNESS Research on AI and Networking at LACNIC 43

Prof. Christian Rothenberg, from FEEC/UNICAMP and Principal Investigator at SMARTNESS, participated in the closing plenary of LACNIC 43 in São Paulo. His talk addressed using artificial intelligence and machine learning in network management, highlighting real-world cases such as YouTube QoE prediction and soft-failure detection in optical networks using network digital twins.

[Read more](#)

Chrysa Papagianni Discusses AI-Native Architectures for 6G at FEEC/UNICAMP Seminar

On May 8, Prof. Chrysa Papagianni (University of Amsterdam) delivered a talk in the IA382 – Seminar in Computer Engineering at FEEC/UNICAMP. She presented an AI-native 6G system architecture, highlighting distributed intelligence, real-time decision-making, and dynamic resource management through the DESIRE6G project, offering a vision for the future of mobile networks.

[Read more](#)

Marina Martinelli, SMARTNESS PhD Student, Joins Futurecom Connect Podcast to Discuss the Future of 5.5G and 6G

In Episode 4 of the Futurecom Connect podcast, SMARTNESS PhD student Marina Martinelli shares her insights on the future of 5.5G and 6G networks. She highlights the importance of AI-driven data center modernization, edge and fog computing, and sustainable infrastructure to meet the demands of a hyperconnected world. The episode also explores Brazil's role in global telecom innovation.

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SMARTNESS Holds 2025 Annual Workshop

On April 24–25, 2025, the Annual Workshop of the CPE SMARTNESS brought together researchers, students, and industry partners at FUNCAMP (UNICAMP) in Campinas. With in-person and online participation, the event featured sessions to define future directions, keynote talks on AI-driven 5G, national and international projects, roundtables with academia and industry, and live tech demos from SMARTNESS teams.

[Read more](#)

SMARTNESS Bootcamp Brings Together Participants for Two Days of Hands-On Learning and Knowledge Sharing

On April 22 and 23, the SMARTNESS Year 02 Bootcamp brought together participants in a hybrid format — online and on-site at UNICAMP — for practical sessions focused on networking technologies, AI/ML, and modern computing tools.

[Read more](#)

Smartness team attends the technical agenda at Ericsson headquarters in Stockholm

From April 7 to 11th, representatives of CPE Smartness visited Ericsson's headquarters in Stockholm to participate in a schedule of technical activities, knowledge exchange, and in-person discussions about the project's progress. The team carried out several meetings with researchers from Ericsson Research, covering topics such as Networks, Artificial Intelligence, Computing, and Software. The agenda also included meetings with Smartness project stakeholders and a visit to the Ericsson Imagine Studio.

[Read more](#)

LEMAC and SMARTNESS Visit INPE to Explore Electromagnetic Material Characterization

On April 16, Eduardo Sartori (TT/SMARTNESS) and LEMAC researchers visited INPE (São José dos Campos) to learn about a system for measuring electromagnetic parameters of materials in the microwave range. The visit included tests on materials used in metasurface research and supported the planning of a similar system at LEMAC, with extended capabilities up to 500GHz.

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